

Supplementary Materials for Collaborative Planning for Catching and Transporting Objects in Unstructured Environments

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1 Modeling Process

Here, we provide a rearticulation of the modeling process for this centralized planning.

To begin with, we formulate the problem as a nonlinear optimal control problem. However, due to the highly nonlinear nature and the high dimensionality of the optimization problem, in this work, we employ differential flatness for simplification without sacrificing optimality. This allows us to express the original robot state and control variables analytically using flat outputs and their finite-dimensional derivatives.

Subsequently, we parameterize the flat outputs using piece-wise polynomials, which naturally ensure motion continuity while reducing the dimensionality of the optimization, thereby enhancing the computational efficiency of the solution. Overall, the application of differential flatness aims to simplify the optimization problem and improve real-time computational efficiency. The specific formulation of the simplified problem can be found in Sec. 2.

Furthermore, we instantiate the formulation of constraints \mathcal{G} in the paper and analytically derive their gradients with respect to the optimization variables (detailed information can be found in our paper), enabling the efficient solution using the quasi-Newton method.

We hope that this clarification of the problem elucidates the framework and modeling process of our approach. Additionally, we have made corresponding revisions to the paper based on your feedback. Thank you again for your valuable suggestions.

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2 Implementation Details on Optimization Problem Solving

Intuitively, we analyze the characteristics of each constraint and subsequently eliminate them individually. As a result, the initial optimization problem is restructured into an unconstrained optimization, allowing us to employ a robust and commonly used quasi-newton method for its solution. Here, we give a detailed introduction to the implementation details.

First, we give the initial formulation of the optimization problem:

$$\min_{\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{T}} \sum_{k=1}^K \left(\int_0^{\tau_k} \boldsymbol{\mu}_k(t)^T \mathbf{W} \boldsymbol{\mu}_k(t) dt + w_T \tau_k \right) + \Psi_{obj}(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{T}) \quad (1a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \boldsymbol{\mu}_k(t) = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_k^{[s]}(t), \forall t \in [0, \tau_k], \quad (1b)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{i,k}^{[s-1]}(0) = \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{0,i,k}, \quad (1c)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{i,j,k}^{[\tilde{d}]}(\delta T_{i,k}) = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{i,j+1,k}^{[\tilde{d}]}(0), \quad (1d)$$

$$T_{i,k} > 0, \quad (1e)$$

$$\mathcal{G}_d(\boldsymbol{\sigma}(t), \dots, \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(s)}(t), t) \preceq 0, \forall d \in \mathcal{D}, \forall t \in [0, \tau_k], \quad (1f)$$

$$\forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n_k\}, \forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, M_{i,k} - 1\},$$

$$\forall k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\},$$

where the definitions of each symbol can be found in our paper. Eq.(1c) is the boundary condition where $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_0$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0$ refer the initial and end states, respectively. Eq.(1d) is the continuity constraint between adjacent polynomials and \tilde{d} is the degree of continuity. Based on the proved optimality condition in previous work [4], it is required that the minimum control-effort piece-wise polynomial achieves $\tilde{d} = 2s - 1$ continuity at waypoints \mathbf{p}_i when the control input dimension is s . For the time positiveness constraint Eq.(1e), we introduced an unconstrained virtual time $\tau_{i,k}$ and applied a diffeomorphism map to eliminate this constraint:

$$T_{i,k} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \tau_{i,k}^2 + \tau_{i,k} + 1 & \tau_{i,k} > 0 \\ \frac{2}{\tau_{i,k}^2 - 2\tau_{i,k} + 2} & \tau_{i,k} \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Thanks to the smooth nature of this mapping, the gradient w.r.t $\tau_{i,k}$ can also be analytically computed using chain rules. We adopt the penalty term S_Σ to relax the feasibility constraints Eq. (1f):

$$S_\Sigma = \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} w_d \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{i=1}^{n_k} \sum_{j=1}^{M_{i,k}} \int_{t=0}^{\delta T_{i,k}} L_1(\mathcal{G}_d(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{i,j,k}(t), \dots, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{i,j,k}^{(s)}(t), t)) dt, \quad (3)$$

$$L_1(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & x \leq 0, \\ -\frac{1}{2a_0^3} x^4 + \frac{1}{a_0^2} x^3 & 0 < x \leq a_0 \\ x - \frac{a_0}{2} & a_0 < x. \end{cases}$$

Here, w_d is the penalty weight corresponding to different kinds of constraints. $L_1(\cdot)$ is a first-order relaxation function to guarantee the continuous differentiability and non-negativity of penalty terms, and $a_0 = 10^{-4}$ is the demarcation point. In the practical implementation, we discretize the integral in Eq.(3) to analytically compute the penalty term. Consequently, the original optimization problem is reformulated into an unconstrained formulation, which can be efficiently solved using the robust L-BFGS algorithm [5].

3 The MPC Used in Real-World Experiment

In this work, the MPC controller serves as a general trajectory tracker to ensure that the robot can effectively follow the planned trajectory. Although we integrated it into our real-world robot system, it is not the primary focus of our contribution, and therefore, we did not allocate significant space for its discussion. We will provide detailed explanations in two aspects:

1. The role of MPC in the system of real-world experiments.

Despite considering the robot’s kinematic model and associated constraints in our trajectory planner, practical execution may still result in cumulative errors due to factors such as system delays, ultimately preventing precise trajectory tracking. To address this issue, we introduce an MPC controller between the system actuators and our planner. This feedback controller continuously adjusts the actuator outputs based on the discrepancy between the desired and current states, ensuring robust trajectory following by the robot. Actually, there is no direct coupling between MPC and the proposed planner.

2. Specific applications of MPC

Regarding the specific application of MPC, we introduce various mathematical symbols, as shown in Tab. 1. It’s important to note that we have omitted the subscripts for distinguishing different agents. Each agent receives the trajectory (\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{T}) and starts analyzing the trajectory from the current time, denoted as the starting time $t_0 = 0$. At a cumulative time t , the differential flatness output $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ can be expressed as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(t) = \mathbf{c}_{i,j}^T \boldsymbol{\beta}(t), \boldsymbol{\beta}(t) := [1, t, \dots, t^5]^T, \quad (4)$$

$$\forall t \in \{t > 0 : \tau_i + (j - 1)T_i < t < \tau_i + jT_i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, M_i\}\}$$

By utilizing the aforementioned expressions, we can obtain the sigma at any given time and its derivatives at various orders. Leveraging the differentiability property, we can further derive the desired body angle θ , velocity v , reference input acceleration a , and steering angle ϕ at any specific time. Each execution cycle of the MPC analyzes K timesteps with a time interval of Δt between each timestep. Here, we define a state point denoted as $\mathbf{X}_k := \{x_k, y_k, \theta_k, v_k\}$. We modify the QP problem formulation for

	Symbol	Definition	Index		Symbol	Definition	Index
1	$\boldsymbol{\sigma}$	the differential flatness outputs $\boldsymbol{\sigma} := (\sigma_x, \sigma_y)^T$	(1)	2	$\mathbf{c}_{i,j}$	the coefficient matrix of j -th piece polynomial in i -th segment of the trajectory $\mathbf{c}_{i,j} \in \mathbb{R}^{2s \times 2}$	(1)
3	τ_i	the start time of the i -th segment	(1)	4	T_i	the duration of each polynomial in i -th segment	(1)
5	K	the prediction horizon of MPC	(2)	6	J	the cost function of MPC	(2)
7	\mathbf{X}_k	the predictive state at k -th step	(2)	8	\mathbf{X}_k^{ref}	the desired state at k -th step of the trajectory	(2)
9	\mathbf{U}_k	the predictive input at k -th step	(2)	10	\mathbf{U}_k^{ref}	the reference input at k -th step of the trajectory	(2)
11	\mathbf{Q}_x	the desired status weights $\mathbf{Q}_x = \text{diag}(w_x, w_y, w_\theta, w_v)$	(2)	12	\mathbf{Q}_u	Desired input weights $\mathbf{Q}_u = \text{diag}(w_a, w_{steer})$	(2)
13	\mathbf{R}	the weight of control volume $\mathbf{R} = \text{diag}(R_a, R_{steer})$	(2)	14	\mathbf{R}_d	the weight of input smoothing $\mathbf{R}_d = \text{diag}(R_{\Delta a}, R_{\Delta steer})$	(2)
15	\mathbf{A}_k	the linearized state transfer matrix at k -th step	(2)	16	\mathbf{B}_k	the linearized input matrix at k -th step	(2)
17	\mathbf{U}_{max}	the maximum input limit $\mathbf{U}_{max} = \text{diag}(a_{max}, \phi_{max})$	(2)	18	\mathbf{X}_{max}	the maximum state limit $\mathbf{X}_{max} = \text{diag}(\infty, \infty, \infty, v_{max})$	(2)
19	\mathbf{U}_{dmax}	maximum input difference limit $\mathbf{U}_{dmax} = \text{diag}(\Delta a_{max}, \Delta \phi_{max})$	(2)	20	L	the wheelbase of the car-like robot	(3)
21	ϕ	the steer input	(3)				

Table 1: Symbol definition in MPC discussion.

MPC optimization based on the reference [1]. The cost function can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\min_{U_k, \forall k} J = & \sum_{k=1}^K \|\mathbf{X}_k - \mathbf{X}_k^{ref}\|_{Q_x}^2 + \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} (\|\mathbf{U}_k - \mathbf{U}_k^{ref}\|_{Q_u}^2 + \|\mathbf{U}_k\|_{\mathbf{R}}^2) + \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \|\mathbf{U}_k - \mathbf{U}_{k-1}\|_{\mathbf{R}_d}^2 \\
\text{s.t. } & \mathbf{X}_{k+1} = \mathbf{A}_k \mathbf{X}_k + \mathbf{B}_k \mathbf{U}_k + \mathbf{C}_k, & k = 0, 1, \dots, K-1, \\
& \|\mathbf{U}_k\| \leq \mathbf{U}_{max}, & k = 0, 1, \dots, K-1, \\
& \|\mathbf{X}_k\| \leq \mathbf{X}_{max}, & k = 1, 2, \dots, K-1, \\
& \|\mathbf{U}_k - \mathbf{U}_{k-1}\| \leq \mathbf{U}_{dmax}, & k = 1, 2, \dots, K-1,
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

In the following section, we will elaborate on the details encountered in the optimization problem. The model employed in this study is the same as described in the paper and can be formulated as:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{s} = v \cos \theta, \\ \dot{y} = v \sin \theta, \\ \dot{\theta} = \frac{v}{L} \tan \phi, \\ \dot{v} = a, \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

To discretize the model, we can write it in the following form:

$$\begin{cases} x_{k+1} = x_k - \hat{v} \cdot \sin \hat{\theta} \cdot (\theta_k - \hat{\theta}) \cdot \Delta t + \cos \hat{\theta} \cdot (v_k - \hat{v}) \cdot \Delta t + \hat{v} \cdot \cos \hat{\theta} \cdot \Delta t, \\ y_{k+1} = y_k + \hat{v} \cdot \cos \hat{\theta} \cdot (\theta_k - \hat{\theta}) \cdot \Delta t + \sin \hat{\theta} \cdot (v_k - \hat{v}) \cdot \Delta t + \hat{v} \cdot \sin \hat{\theta} \cdot \Delta t, \\ v_{k+1} = v_k + (a_k - \hat{a}) \cdot \Delta t + \hat{a} \cdot \Delta t, \\ \theta_{k+1} = \theta_k + (\omega_k - \hat{\omega}) \cdot \Delta t + \hat{\omega} \cdot \Delta t. \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

When solving the problem, we linearize each point and can express it as:

$$\mathbf{X}_{k+1} = \mathbf{A}(\hat{\mathbf{X}}, \hat{\mathbf{U}}) \mathbf{X}_k + \mathbf{B}(\hat{\mathbf{X}}, \hat{\mathbf{U}}) \mathbf{U}_k + \mathbf{C}(\hat{\mathbf{X}}, \hat{\mathbf{U}}) \tag{8}$$

Finally, the MPC problem is solved using the OSQP library [2].

4 Ablation Experiments

We have conducted additional experiments on catching and transporting to better demonstrate its effectiveness. Furthermore, we have expanded the comparative analysis and discussion based on the original experiments.

1. Efficient and high-quality trajectory generation is the foundation for time-constrained catching and transporting tasks. From the comparative experiments, it is evident that other methods have significant disadvantages in terms of success rate and computation time. In scenarios where other methods generally exhibit lower trajectory generation efficiency, generating catching and transporting trajectories while considering additional constraints and costs will result in lower success rate and longer computation time. Therefore, for collaborative tasks that require considering more constraints and costs, other methods are less suitable.

2. To demonstrate the effectiveness of our method in catching and transporting tasks, we have conducted several constraint ablation experiments to showcase the positive impact of our proposed method on collaboration. By removing the net adaptive catching or size safety components, the spatio-temporal trajectories reflect the effectiveness of our proposed method in catching and transporting.
 - (a) As shown in Fig. 1, we compared the trajectories with the adaptive catching component removed. In the landing phase, the robot team did not tend towards the target from the initial positions and did not proactively increase the area of the net to enhance catching probability. This demonstrates the effectiveness of our proposed method in catching.
 - (b) We compared the trajectories with the net size safety constraint removed. In most cases, it is observed that in order to maximize the probability of successful catching, agents engaged in aggressive movements, which violated the safety margin of the net size, as illustrated in the third column of Fig. 1.
3. We have compared our method by incorporating catching and transporting task constraints and costs into the second best-performing method, FOTP, which is suitable for adding collaborative constraints in the benchmark.

Figure 1: In rows labeled 'a', 'b', and 'c', we present three distinct scenarios. In columns '1', '2', and '3', we conduct comparative experiments involving identical initial conditions, identical objectives, and varying functional applications. We display the state of the robot team at the beginning, end of trajectory execution, and when the target is reached. And the target that needs to be caught is visualized as a red sphere.

5 Discussion on η

In order to model the vehicle using a differential flatness model, we introduce η to represent the forward and backward motion of the robot within a segment of the trajectory, as

shown in Eq.(9).

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} v = \eta \sqrt{\dot{\sigma}_x^2 + \dot{\sigma}_y^2}, \\ \theta = \arctan 2(\eta \dot{\sigma}_x, \eta \dot{\sigma}_y), \\ a_t = \eta(\dot{\sigma}_x \ddot{\sigma}_x + \dot{\sigma}_y \ddot{\sigma}_y) / \sqrt{\dot{\sigma}_x^2 + \dot{\sigma}_y^2}, \\ a_n = \eta(\dot{\sigma}_x \ddot{\sigma}_y - \dot{\sigma}_y \ddot{\sigma}_x) / \sqrt{\dot{\sigma}_x^2 + \dot{\sigma}_y^2}, \\ \phi = \arctan \left(\eta(\dot{\sigma}_x \ddot{\sigma}_y - \dot{\sigma}_y \ddot{\sigma}_x) L / (\dot{\sigma}_x^2 + \dot{\sigma}_y^2)^{\frac{3}{2}} \right), \\ \kappa = \eta(\dot{\sigma}_x \ddot{\sigma}_y - \dot{\sigma}_y \ddot{\sigma}_x) / (\dot{\sigma}_x^2 + \dot{\sigma}_y^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}, \end{array} \right. \quad (9)$$

where η is a discrete variable with values $\{-1, 1\}$. If used as a decision variable in the optimization problem, it would be challenging to handle due to its strong nonlinearity and discreteness. As we did not optimize the discrete variable η , it is acknowledged that we sacrifice a certain solution space and optimality. However, this does not imply that the trajectory planning method proposed in this paper loses a significant degree of freedom. This is because of the following reasons:

- (1) The determination of η is based on the initial guess provided by the Hybrid A* search. If two segments with opposite η values are determined, it is highly likely that an Ackerman-based robot will require both forward and backward movements to reach the desired state. In such cases, it is appropriate to focus on adjusting the positions and orientations of the gear shifting points generated by forward and backward movements, aiming to achieve smoother trajectories and ensure that the gear shifting points satisfy task constraints, such as net safety.
- (2) In segments of the trajectory where the forward and backward motion differs, the gear shifting point, where the transition between the two occurs, divides the trajectory into two parts with opposite η values. We incorporate the position and orientation (x, y, θ) of the common gear shifting point between two different segments of the trajectory into the decision variables. This provides sufficient freedom for trajectory optimization by adjusting the gear shifting point. Experimental verification has shown that in certain scenarios, the initial values provided by the front-end are rough and conservative. The back-end optimization can then adjust the gear shifting point, resulting in a significantly smoother overall trajectory, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: (a) For initial values that are relatively coarse, the backend performs simultaneous optimization of the entire trajectory, including the gear shifting points. (b) During the optimization of gear shifting points, safety constraints are maintained, ensuring the attainment of a smooth trajectory over the entire segment. (c) In cases involving trajectories with multiple forward and backward transitions, simultaneous optimization of all gear shifting points is achievable.

6 Forward and Backward Movement of Robotic Team

In fact, during the implementation of our simulation experiments, there were several setups (including input environment, initial state, and target state) where it was necessary to have both forward and backward movements to reach the target state. However, due to limitations in the length of the paper, we did not emphasize this aspect specifically.

To address this concern, we have included trajectory planning results showcasing both forward and backward movements in different scenarios for both single agent and multi-agent systems. As shown in Fig. 3, the blue trajectory represents the initial guess, the red trajectory depicts the solution result, the green rectangle denotes the initial state, and the purple rectangle represents the target state. We have also included a concise version of these results in the revised version of the manuscript.

Figure 3: On the left column, the initial states of robot teams in different environments are displayed, along with the desired states represented by blue arrows. On the right column, the proposed method generates trajectories for robot teams that encompass both forward and backward motion.

7 Details on Comparative Experiments

We will further supplement the information on the implementation of the comparative experiments and include it in the manuscript. To ensure fairness in our comparative experiments, we conducted the experiments under identical scenarios and inputs.

1. To ensure fairness in the comparative experiments, we provided the same initial guess for methods using the Hybrid A* algorithm [6]. For each robot, the algorithm searches for a collision-free path considering the initial and final states of each robot and the environmental obstacles. The search process rejects motion primitives that result in collisions with obstacles and eventually obtains a feasible sequence of states and corresponding inputs. These feasible states and inputs are then used as suitable initial values for each method. It is worth mentioning that CL-CBS [7] is a search-based method that obtains collision-free trajectories, so it does not require an initial guess. DMPC [8], on the other hand, continuously solves the optimization problem during

planning to generate trajectories for the robot team, and therefore does not rely on an initial guess.

2. Concerning the cost function, in our comparative experiments, our primary focus lies in assessing the efficiency and quality of each method in generating trajectories for the robot team. This serves as the foundational aspect for achieving efficient catching and transporting. To align with the inherent characteristics of each method and to enhance the likelihood of success, we have employed the original formulations of the cost function as presented in their respective source papers. Broadly, these formulations involve considerations related to trajectory smoothness and total duration. However, each method employs different approaches to achieve smoothness, as indicated in the Tab. 2.
3. Regarding the relaxation of final states, we did not incorporate any relaxation of final states in the comparative experiments. This decision was made to ensure fairness in the comparative evaluation. Additionally, the relaxation of final states is mainly introduced to facilitate smoother and safer trajectories after catching the target.

8 More Comparative Experiments for FOTP

It is worth mentioning that we conducted several comparative experiments for FOTP [9] under different time weightings. This is because there exists a trade-off relationship between trajectory duration and smoothness. As detailed in Section Sec. 7, the cost function of FOTP can be expressed as:

$$J = T + w \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{N_v} \left(\sum_{j=0}^H (a_{i,j}^2 + v_{i,j}^2 \cdot \omega_{i,j}^2) \right) \quad (10)$$

, where w represents the weight assigned to the time duration. In our previous version of the manuscript, we set $w = 0.1$ following the original method. However, FOTP achieves significantly longer trajectory durations compared to other methods in exchange for lower acceleration costs. Consequently, to understand how the trajectory duration of FOTP compares to other methods while maintaining a similar level of smoothness, we conducted comparative experiments with $w = 0.01$ and $w = 0.001$, under the same environment and initial/final states as the previous version. The results are shown in Tab. 3. In order to control the method at the same TRAVEL time level, we adopt the result of $w = 0.001$.

	Method	Cost Function	Definition
1	FOTP [9]	$J = T + w \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{N_v} \left(\sum_{j=0}^H (a_{i,j}^2 + v_{i,j}^2 \cdot \omega_{i,j}^2) \right)$	<p>T is the time duration of the trajectories, w is the weight of smooth penalty, N_v is the number of agents, H is the number of planning timesteps, and $a_{i,j}, v_{i,j}, \omega_{i,j}$ is the acceleration input, velocity, angular velocity of the i-th agent at j-th timestep.</p>
2	MNHP	$J = \sum_{i=1}^{N_v} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{H-1} \Delta u_{i,j}^T P \Delta u_{i,j} + \sum_{j=1}^H \bar{z}_{i,j}^T Q \bar{z}_{i,j} \right)$	<p>$\Delta u_{i,j} = u_{i,j} - u_{i,j-1}$ is the differences between two successive control inputs, and $\bar{z}_{i,j}$ the deviation between the trajectory and the reference trajectory. $P \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ and $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ are two positive definite weighting matrices.</p>
3	DMPC	$J = \sum_{j=H-\kappa}^H q_k \ \hat{\mathbf{z}}_i[j j_t] - \mathbf{z}_{d,i}\ _2^2 + \sum_{c=0}^r \alpha_c \int_0^{t_h} \left\ \frac{d^c}{dt^c} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_i(t) \right\ _2^2 dt$	<p>The first term aim to minimize the sum of errors between the positions and the goal state $\mathbf{z}_{d,i}$ at the last $\kappa < H$ timesteps. The second term aim to minimize a weighted combination of the sum of squared derivatives.</p>
4	SCP	$J = \sum_{i=1}^{N_v} \sum_{q=1}^{N_v} \sum_{j=1}^H w_{i,q} a_{i,j}^T a_{q,j}$	<p>$w_{i,j} = 1$ when $i = j$ and $w_{i,j} = 0$ otherwise, which tends to induce smooth trajectories with low curvatures.</p>

Table 2: The cost functions of various methods being compared share a common set of symbol definitions.

Method	Success Rate	Time(s)			Average Travel Distance(m)	Average Acceration Cost(m^2s^{-3})
		Computation	Mean Travel	Longest Travel		
Proposed, N = 8	100%	0.280	5.956	6.918	84.461	244.925
Proposed, N = 14	100%	0.707	6.067	6.841	145.002	205.204
Proposed, N = 20	100%	1.186	6.328	7.151	207.469	196.532
Proposed, N = 26	100%	1.900	6.387	8.216	271.725	218.752
$w = 0.001$						
FOTP, N = 8	100%	4.897	6.169	6.169	81.462	286.648
FOTP, N = 14	100%	37.801	6.957	6.957	149.151	245.775
FOTP, N = 20	100%	147.214	7.835	7.835	222.223	204.270
FOTP, N = 26	100%	376.645	8.888	8.888	297.745	154.748
$w = 0.01$						
FOTP, N = 8	100%	4.970	8.492	8.492	81.545	109.782
FOTP, N = 14	100%	69.084	9.780	9.780	146.804	81.110
FOTP, N = 20	100%	159.535	10.847	10.847	214.560	65.331
FOTP, N = 26	100%	384.098	12.100	12.100	287.217	57.885
$w = 0.1$						
FOTP, N = 8	100%	5.690	13.789	13.789	82.561	28.376
FOTP, N = 14	100%	50.111	15.254	15.254	144.233	20.179
FOTP, N = 20	100%	135.057	17.028	17.028	209.591	16.890
FOTP, N = 26	100%	344.703	18.332	18.332	277.040	14.209

Table 3: The experimental data of FOTP under different time weight w

9 Discussion on The Local Minimum

The objective of the trajectory optimization is to solve a multi-stage Linear Quadratic Minimum Time (LQMT) problem [4], which is non-convex and non-linear. Furthermore, when it comes to the whole-body inter-agent avoidance and adaptive catching, there exist highly nonlinear constraints and costs. Therefore, we cannot guarantee that gradient descent methods will attain the globally optimal solution in optimization.

Local minimum refers to the high-quality trajectory of a robot team obtained through optimization within the topological environment based on the current initial input values. Our experiments demonstrate that the optimized trajectory is smoother compared to the initial values and eliminates infeasible points on the initial trajectory, as shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. However, we acknowledge that, in the context of nonlinear optimization, the initial values play a crucial role as they affect the quality of the final solution and the solution time. In practical engineering applications, we employ the widely-used and efficient Hybrid A* algorithm [6] to obtain the initial values, which can generate a curvature-constrained and collision-free path. Nevertheless, it is possible that the initial values may not completely satisfy all constraints or achieve successful capture at certain points. However, extensive

experimentation has demonstrated that thanks to the powerful optimization capability of our backend planning algorithm, the optimized trajectory can often accomplish the tasks of catching and transporting while ensuring safety and dynamic feasibility.

10 Discussion on The Approximations Applied

We introduce the smoothing approximations in order to achieve reasonable gradient descent directions throughout the entire optimization process, ensuring that the solver efficiently and accurately converges to local minimum points. In practical engineering applications, we believe that the errors caused by this smoothing term can be almost negligible in determining the feasibility of finding a solution, which is further validated by the high success rate observed in experiments. However, we acknowledge that in principle, smoothing can sometimes lead to planning failures in situations where success should have been achieved. Nevertheless, we consider smoothing to be unavoidable because there exist non-differentiable points in the signed distance between two convex polygons in physical terms. Additionally, despite the introduction of smoothing, our full-shape collision avoidance method is more precise compared to particle-based models. We provide explanations regarding the details of the approximations, the algorithm itself, and the application specifics:

- (1) The inclusion of smoothing terms aims to obtain better gradients within a small neighborhood around the constraint edge when performing gradient descent. This approach prevents the occurrence of abnormal gradients that may result in the failure of gradient descent in that region. Accordingly, the parameters related to the smoothing process are set to very small values and only take effect within a tiny neighborhood of critical points, such as α in LSE and $\epsilon \in \mathbb{R}^+$ in $L(x)$ of adaptive catching. This effectively mitigates the influence of the approximations on the optimization process.
- (2) In fact, in our simulation or comparative experiments, we have not encountered instances where the smoothing leads to non-existent solutions. On the contrary, our method has demonstrated a higher success rate compared to conservative approaches. Although we employ smoothing, the effective solution space for obstacle avoidance, considering the whole-body aspect, remains larger compared to conservative particle-based models.
- (3) To tackle safety issues arising from infeasible solutions, there are some details:
 - (a) With the cost Ψ illustrated in IV.C, adaptive catching encourages the active expansion of the net when catching target and bringing the center of the net closer to the target. This provides a margin for catching, and has been observed to significantly improve the success rate of catching in simulations.
 - (b) Assigning greater weights to environmental obstacle avoidance and inter-agent collision avoidance during the solution process, prioritizing agent safety.
 - (c) Setting conservative values for physical parameters related to net size safety and net topological safety, allowing for a margin of safety in net safety.

In summary, these three points mitigate the impact of approximations on the solution space of our method. While it is true that we may encounter a reduction in solution space theoretically, our approach offers greater advantages in terms of success rate and computation time compared to conservative methods. Furthermore, through the design of our method itself, we effectively achieve coordinated catching and transporting in practical applications while balancing computational efficiency, success rate, and solution quality.

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